

**Zinc-Biofortified Wheat Intake and Zinc Status Biomarkers in Men: Randomized
Controlled Trial (RCT)**

**Erinn M. Liong¹, Christine M. McDonald^{1,2}, Jung Suh¹, Jamie L. Westcott³, Carmen P.
Wong⁴, Coralie Signorell¹, Janet C. King^{1,5}**

Author Affiliations:

1. Children's Hospital Oakland Research Institute, Oakland, CA
2. Department of Pediatrics, University of California, San Francisco, CA
3. School of Medicine, University of Colorado, Denver, CO
4. School of Biological and Population Health Sciences, Oregon State University, Corvallis, OR
5. Department of Nutritional Sciences and Toxicology, University of California, Berkeley, CA

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Corresponding Author: JC King, Children's Hospital Oakland Research Institute, 5700 MLK Jr Way, Oakland, CA; 510-450-7939; jking829@berkeley.edu

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Abbreviations: AA: arachidonic acid, DGLA: dihomo-gamma-linolenic acid, DTT: dithiothreitol, FADS1: fatty acid desaturase 1, FADS2: fatty acid desaturase 2, GLA: gamma-

linolenic acid, GSH: glutathione, LA: linoleic acid, MP1: metabolic period 1, MP2: metabolic period 2, MP3: metabolic period 3

1 **Abstract**

2 **Background:** Biofortification is a novel method for improving the nutritional value of grains.

3 Wheat is widely consumed worldwide. Thus, wheat zinc biofortification may improve the zinc
4 status of populations.

5 **Objective:** We determined the effect of consuming zinc-biofortified wheat on plasma zinc
6 concentrations and biomarkers of zinc-dependent functions in a controlled feeding study.

7 **Methods:** Thirty-six healthy adult men, age 18 to 51 years, participated in a 10-week zinc
8 controlled feeding trial. After a two week run-in period (Metabolic Period 1: MP1) (9.3 mg Zn/d
9 and 2.1 g total phytate/d) to standardize zinc status, the participants consumed bread made from
10 zinc-biofortified wheat (10.9 mg Zn/d) with no additional phytate (0.6 g/d total phytate) for six
11 weeks (MP2). During the final two weeks (MP3), half of the men took a 25 mg zinc supplement
12 daily to determine if the supplement further altered zinc status biomarkers. Repeated measures
13 linear regression methods were used to compare plasma zinc concentrations, fatty acid
14 desaturase (FADS) activities, glutathione (GSH) concentrations, and DNA strand breaks
15 assessed at enrollment and the end of each metabolic period.

16 **Results:** Plasma zinc concentrations did not change throughout the study. From the end of MP1
17 to the end of MP2, the conversion of LA (linoleic acid) to GLA (gamma-linolenic acid) (FADS2
18 activity) increased from 0.020 to 0.025 ($P=0.02$) and the conversion of DGLA (dihomo-gamma-
19 linolenic acid) to AA (arachidonic acid) (FADS1 activity) decreased from 6.37 to 5.53 ($P=0.01$).
20 GSH levels and DNA strand breaks did not change. Zinc supplementation (25 mg/d) in MP3 did
21 not alter any of the endpoints.

22 **Conclusions:** In healthy adult men, a 1.6 mg/d increase in dietary zinc from biofortified wheat
23 modified FADS2 and FADS1 activities without changing DNA damage, plasma zinc, or GSH

- 24 concentrations demonstrating that FADS activities are more sensitive to small changes in zinc
- 25 consumed with a meal.
- 26 **Keywords:** biofortification, zinc, wheat, DNA strand breaks, essential fatty acid metabolism

27 **Introduction**

28 Zinc is involved in numerous metabolic processes involving lipid and carbohydrate
29 metabolism, DNA replication, and signal transduction between cells. Thus, zinc deficiency can
30 cause defective functions in many organ systems that increase the risk of infections, reduce
31 appetite, impair reproductive function, and reduce physical growth (1). Based on the prevalence
32 of child stunting and the availability of zinc in the food supply, it is estimated that approximately
33 17% of the world's population is at risk of zinc deficiency (2).

34 Studies of zinc supplementation show an improvement in zinc nutrition and a reduction
35 in pneumonia and diarrhea in children (3-5). However, widespread distribution of zinc
36 supplements to vulnerable populations in low- and middle-income countries is difficult to
37 achieve. Enhancing the zinc content of commonly used grains through biofortification is an
38 inexpensive way to enhance zinc intakes for many populations throughout the world.
39 Biofortification, achieved through adding nutrients to fertilizers applied to growing crops and/or
40 the selective breeding of crop strains to maximize the potential for nutrient uptake from the soil,
41 has been used to increase the zinc content of plant food staples i.e., wheat, maize, and rice (6, 7).
42 With support from Harvest Plus, Velu Govindan and his co-workers at International Maize and
43 Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT) in Mexico have developed a zinc-biofortified wheat that
44 provides a 5-8% greater yield along with a higher zinc concentration than other popular varieties
45 (8). This wheat strain, *Bari Gom 33*, is a cross between Kachu and Solala and is the zinc-
46 biofortified strain used in this study. When tested in Bangladesh, *Bari Gom 33*, a refined white
47 flour, provided 7-8 ppm zinc over local wheat varieties (8). Previous studies have shown that
48 zinc absorption is increased when biofortified wheat is consumed (9, 10), but the effect of
49 consuming the zinc-biofortified wheat on biomarkers of zinc status has not been investigated.

50 Dietary zinc intake, height-for-age in children under 5, and plasma or serum zinc
51 concentrations are recommended indicators of zinc status at the population level (11). However,
52 these biomarkers have limitations that make evaluating zinc status a challenge (11). Recent
53 research has shown that several metabolic biomarkers may be influenced by dietary zinc. Those
54 novel biomarkers include aspects of omega-six fatty acid metabolism, DNA strand breaks, and
55 blood glutathione (GSH) concentrations (12-15). The increase in oxidative stress associated with
56 zinc deficiency may increase DNA damage (11, 16, 17). Also, the oxidative stress induced by
57 zinc-deficiency may increase the oxidation of glutathione (GSH) to glutathione disulfide (GSSG)
58 (18).

59 Adequate zinc intake is required to support omega-6 fatty acid metabolism. Fatty acid
60 desaturase 2 (FADS2) and fatty acid desaturase 1 (FADS1) are iron-dependent enzymes that are
61 essential for metabolizing linoleic acid (LA) to arachidonic acid (AA) (**Figure 1**). Prior studies
62 have identified an association between low dietary zinc intake and FADS1/2 activities (19).
63 FADS2 is a Δ -6-desaturase and FADS1 is a Δ -5-desaturase (20). The LA:DGLA (linoleic
64 acid:dihomo-gamma-linolenic acid) ratio is a marker of FADS2 activity, and it has been shown
65 to be a sensitive and specific way to assess zinc status (13, 21). The LA:DGLA ratio also
66 includes the Δ -6-elongase activity; the GLA:LA (linoleic acid:gamma-linolenic acid) ratio is a
67 more specific estimate of FADS2 activity.

68 The primary objective of this study was to determine the effect of consuming a diet based
69 on zinc-biofortified wheat on biomarkers of zinc status, i.e., plasma zinc concentrations, DNA
70 strand breaks, FADS activities, and glutathione metabolism, in adult men residing in the San
71 Francisco Bay Area of California. In addition, we investigated whether the addition of a 25 mg/d
72 zinc supplement for two weeks further altered the zinc status biomarkers.

73 **Methods and Materials**

74 *Study design and participants*

75 A total of 45 men 18-50 years of age were recruited to participate in a 10-week non-
76 blinded, randomized, controlled feeding trial to evaluate the effect of zinc-biofortified wheat on
77 biomarkers of zinc function. The primary outcome measures of the study were FADS1 and
78 FADS2 activities. The power calculation was performed based off the effect size estimated from
79 FADS1 activity measured in plasma samples generated from Zyba et al., where subjects
80 consumed a low zinc diet (6 mg/d) and switched to a zinc replete diet (10 mg/d) (12). A sample
81 size of 40 men was estimated to have approximately 90% power to replicate the FADS1 activity
82 findings observed. Four cohorts of 5 to 18 participants each were studied. Subjects were
83 recruited by word of mouth and by advertising to student community groups at the University of
84 California, Berkeley. Exclusion criteria included self-reports of any chronic or acute diseases,
85 being underweight ($BMI < 18.5 \text{ kg/m}^2$), smoking or alcohol abuse, use of illicit drugs, regular use
86 of prescription medications, or consuming supplemental zinc within four weeks of enrollment.
87 Underweight men were excluded because we did not want to limit their caloric intake. Women
88 were excluded because zinc status varies with the menstrual cycle, which makes it difficult to
89 link the biomarker analysis to zinc measurements (22, 23). Men that were interested and eligible
90 to participate reviewed the adult consent form with the study coordinator and was given a copy
91 of the consent form along with staff contact information. Men were asked to verbally summarize
92 the study to the study staff in order to make sure he thoroughly understood the study.

93 The study was divided into three metabolic periods (**Figure 2**). During the 14-day
94 baseline period (Metabolic Period 1, MP1), the men consumed a controlled diet that provided 9.3
95 mg of zinc and 2.1 g of phytate per day; 1.5 g of the 2.1 g of phytate was added as a solution to

96 wheat bread baked by the research team to induce a modest reduction in zinc absorption. Phytate
97 limits zinc absorption by binding zinc, making the zinc insoluble and unavailable for absorption
98 in the intestine. The level of phytate fed in this study is about four-times higher than the usual
99 intake from American diets (24). This reduction in zinc absorption in MP1 served to create a
100 population of men in a similar state of zinc nutrition, which was necessary to standardize the
101 amount of zinc absorbed from the biofortified wheat in Metabolic Period 2. In the 42-day
102 second metabolic period (MP2), the men consumed a diet that provided 10.9 mg Zn/d without
103 additional phytate; 6.3 mg of the 10.9 mg Zn/d was provided by bread that was made with zinc-
104 biofortified wheat flour. In the 14-day third MP (MP3), the 36 men remaining in the study
105 received different interventions depending on their group assignment: Group P ($n=19$) continued
106 to receive the 10.9 mg Zn/d diet fed in MP2 with a cornstarch placebo pill, and Group S ($n=17$)
107 continued to consume the MP2 diet with a 25 mg/d zinc supplement (in the form of zinc
108 gluconate) that was taken daily in the fasting state, 30 minutes before breakfast. For each cohort,
109 as the men were recruited, they were alternately assigned a number (1 or 2), which corresponded
110 to either the placebo or supplement group.

111 At enrollment, the men completed a demographic survey that included questions about
112 their physical activity and medical history; a fasting baseline blood sample was taken. They also
113 received all of the food to consume during the next seven days. The men lived at home
114 throughout the 11-week study, but they came to the study site on a weekly basis to obtain food
115 for the following week. The study dietitian conducted private weekly interviews with each
116 participant that focused on assessing diet compliance. Fasting morning blood samples were also
117 obtained after completion of each metabolic period (days 15, 57, and 70) (**Figure 2**). General
118 health status and anthropometric measurements (i.e., body weight, height, waist circumference,

119 heart rate, and systolic and diastolic blood pressure) were also performed on each of the blood
120 draw days.

121 *Study diet*

122 The study diet consisted of a repeating 4-day cycle menu. All food and beverage intake
123 was limited to that provided by the study. The dietary components included bread baked with
124 either the control or biofortified wheat, as well as fresh fruits, vegetables, and frozen, prepared
125 entrees. The standard study diet was based on typical diets of adult men and pre-study diet
126 information from the participants. Some men required individual modifications to their dietary
127 energy to maintain their body weight. That was achieved by providing additional energy from
128 zinc-free supplementary food items, including frittatas (made with zinc-free egg whites), raisins,
129 cookies, and a rice beverage. The University of Minnesota Nutrition Data System for Research
130 (NDSR 2016, Minneapolis, Minnesota) was used to determine the macronutrient composition of
131 the diet. Those data were supplemented with nutritional information obtained from the
132 manufacturers' packaging for some entrees. Participants were given daily menu checklists each
133 week to indicate what foods were consumed or not eaten. The participants were asked to return
134 any uneaten food at the end of the week. The amount returned was subtracted from their overall
135 intakes.

136 For all three metabolic periods, the baseline diet provided a total of 2647 kcal/d, of which
137 58% of the energy was carbohydrate, 10% was protein, and 32% was fat. The carbohydrate,
138 protein, and fat contents of the diet were 384 g/d, 66 g/d, and 94 g/d, respectively. The amount
139 of saturated fat was 28 g/d. The zinc and phytate content of the study diet are described in **Table**
140 **1**.

141 *Blood sampling and processing*

142 At each of the blood draws, 22 mL of blood was sampled from the antecubital vein of the
143 recumbent subjects using Becton-Dickson (BD) Insyte catheters with appropriate vacutainers.
144 Trace element-free certified vacutainers were used for the zinc analysis aliquots. Plasma was
145 separated from blood using a Sorvall RC-5C centrifuge. Blood in 10 mL tubes was treated with
146 K₂EDTA and spun at 1500 x g for 15 minutes at 4 °C. The plasma was collected and separated
147 into 510 µL aliquots per 1.5 mL tubes for analysis. In addition to plasma collection, a separate
148 set of whole blood samples were cryopreserved for DNA damage assessment using the Comet
149 assay. All samples were stored at -20 °C or -80 °C until analyses.

150 *Laboratory analysis*

151 The zinc content of the baseline study diets and the breads were determined by atomic
152 absorption spectrometry (AAS) at the University of Colorado, Denver. Samples were
153 homogenized, dried, and wet ashed until all organic matter was removed. The samples were then
154 reconstituted in HCl and analyzed for total zinc using Perkin Elmer Atomic Absorption
155 AAnalyst 400 (Waltham, MA 02451).

156 The phytate content, plasma zinc concentration, fatty acids, and glutathione analyses
157 were performed at Children's Hospital Oakland Research Institute (CHORI). Blood samples
158 were prepared and analyzed for DNA strand break assessments at Oregon State University.

159 The phytate content of the diet and breads was determined by the modified Makower
160 method (25) and as previously described (26).

161 Plasma zinc concentrations were measured by inductively coupled plasma-optical
162 emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) using an Agilent 5100 SVDV ICP-OES Spectrometer, as
163 previously described (12).

164 Essential fatty acids were quantified using liquid chromatography-tandem mass
165 spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). The analysis was performed with an Agilent 1290 Infinity
166 Quaternary liquid chromatography system and Agilent 6490 Triple Quadrupole mass
167 spectrometer at CHORI. Arachidonic acid (AA), and linoleic acid (LA), gamma-linolenic acid
168 (GLA), and dihomo-gamma-linolenic acid (DGLA) were targeted. Samples were prepared
169 according to a previously described method (27).

170 Plasma amino acid analysis was performed using the EZ:faast™ LC/MS Physiological
171 (Free) Amino Acids Kit (Phenomenex). Samples were incubated with 10 mM dithiothreitol
172 (DTT) for one hour, then processed according to kit instructions. Plasma glutathione (GSH)
173 concentration data was determined as part of this analysis.

174 The Comet assay was used to measure DNA strand breaks. To process cryopreserved
175 whole blood, cryopreserved cells were rapidly thawed in a 37°C water bath. 100 mL of samples
176 were transferred to 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tubes containing 1 mL ice cold phosphate-buffered
177 saline (PBS) and mixed gently. The samples were centrifuged at 300 g for 5 minutes at room
178 temperature. The supernatant was removed and cells were resuspended in 600 mL ice cold PBS.
179 To make the slides, 50 mL of prepared sample was added to 250 mL of 0.5% low melt agarose.
180 After gently mixing, 50 mL of the sample-agarose solution was spread onto both circles of each
181 Comet slide. The slides were laid flat and covered in a cold drawer to protect them from light
182 and dust for 30 minutes. The flat slides were then covered with cold lysis solution (Trevigen)
183 and incubated in 4°C for 1 hour or overnight. The slides were then put into an electrophoresis
184 bath with alkali buffer at room temperature for 20 minutes. Electrophoresis was run for 20
185 minutes at 25 V and 300 mA. The slides were then removed and rinsed twice in water, 5
186 minutes each. After, slides were incubated with 70% ethanol for 5 minutes and dried in 37°C

187 oven and stored in the dark at room temperature until ready for staining and scoring. DNA was
188 stained using SYBR gold nucleic acid stain (Life Technologies) for 30 minutes at room
189 temperature in the dark. Stained slides were rinsed once in water, and dried in 37°C oven for 15
190 mins. Tail moments from 100 cells per subjects were scored using Comet Assay IV software
191 (Instem, Bury St Edmunds, United Kingdom).

192 *Statistical analysis*

193 Descriptive statistics were used to summarize key characteristics of the study population
194 at the time of enrollment. Outliers were detected by identifying data points that were above and
195 below 1.5 times above and below the 25th and the 75th percentile values. Effects of dietary
196 intervention on plasma zinc, fatty acids, FADS1 and FADS2 activities, and GSH concentrations
197 were compared by fitting the linear mixed model with the diet phase as the fixed effect and
198 subject as the random intercept using the lme4 R package v1.1. The model applied was as
199 follows: $\text{lmer}(\text{observation} \sim \text{Diet Phase} + (1|\text{subject}))$. Effects of zinc supplementation between
200 the end of MP2 and the end of MP3 were compared by fitting the following linear mixed model:
201 $\text{lmer}(\text{observation} \sim \text{Group} * \text{Time} + (1|\text{Subject}))$. All statistical analyses were performed using R
202 studio v1.3.959 with R version 4.0.1. A P value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

203 *Ethics approval*

204 This study was approved under the CHORI Institutional Review Board.

205 **Results**

206 Between July 2017 and May 2018, 45 participants were enrolled into one of four study
207 cohorts. Although 45 participants were initially enrolled, nine men had incomplete datasets due
208 to early attrition from the study or, in the case of one man, deviation from the study diet.
209 Reasons for participant attrition were finding the study too difficult to manage in a dorm,
210 experiencing intense cravings and energy fluctuations, not replying to our team and picking up
211 his food, and declining to participate after the first week. These nine men were excluded from
212 the study analysis because they either did not provide plasma samples for any timepoint or only
213 provided plasma at the beginning of the study for the baseline measurements. The characteristics
214 of the 36 men completing the study are summarized in **Table 2**. Baseline characteristics did not
215 differ between the zinc supplemented and unsupplemented groups in MP3. The mean age of the
216 men was 26 years; 44% were Asian, and 33% were Caucasian. Four men had a BMI >30 kg/m²,
217 but only one of the men was also classified as obese by having a waist circumference >102 cm.
218 The mean plasma zinc concentration was 79.4 µg/dL for the study population of 36 men at
219 enrollment.

220 On average, the men maintained normal fasting plasma zinc concentrations throughout
221 the study (**Table 3**). Thirteen men had low plasma zinc values (<70 µg/dL), but only at one or
222 two of the four time points measured, which may have reflected a non-fasting state at the time of
223 blood draw. Plasma zinc concentrations did not change significantly throughout the study.
224 However, an upward trend from 77.8 µg/dL to 83.1 µg/dL was seen in the men who took the 25
225 mg zinc supplement daily during two weeks in MP3.

226 FADS2 activity, as determined by the GLA:LA ratio, increased from 0.020 to 0.025
227 ($P=0.02$) during MP2 when the participants were consuming 10.9 mg Zn/d (of which 6.3 mg was

228 provided by the bread made with biofortified wheat flour) without additional phytate. The
229 concentration of GLA increased while that of LA did not change (**Supplementary Table 2**).
230 Over the same period, FADS1 activity, as determined by the AA:DGLA ratio, decreased from
231 6.37 to 5.53 ($P=0.01$) (**Table 3**). The concentration of DGLA increased and that of AA did not
232 change (**Supplementary Table 2**). There was no change in either FADS2 or FADS1 activity
233 during MP3 when the 25 mg/d of supplemental zinc was given to half of the men (**Table 4**).

234 Although there were no significant differences in tail moments, a measure of DNA strand
235 breaks, between the end of MP1 and the end of MP2, levels at both time points were
236 significantly lower than those at baseline (**Figure 3A**). Supplementation with 25 mg Zn/d for 2
237 weeks for the 16 men in MP3S did not change the number of DNA strand breaks (**Figure 3B**).

238 Plasma glutathione levels trended upwards from 16.4 μM at baseline to 18.7 μM at the
239 end of MP1 and 18.5 μM at the end of MP2 ($P=0.08$) (**Table 3**). Zinc supplementation in MP3
240 did not affect plasma glutathione concentration (**Table 4**).

241 Discussion

242 The effect of zinc-biofortified wheat on biomarkers of zinc status was studied in healthy
243 men during a 10-week, randomized, controlled feeding trial. The plasma zinc concentrations
244 were unresponsive to the 1.6 mg/d increase in total dietary zinc between the end of MP1 and the
245 end of MP2 and to the addition of 25 mg/d supplemental zinc in half of the men during MP3.
246 The plasma fatty acids analysis showed that FADS2 activity increased significantly during MP2,
247 the 42-day period during which subjects received a total of 10.9 mg Zn/d (of which 6.3 mg was
248 provided by the bread made with biofortified wheat flour) and the additional 1.5 g/d of phytate
249 that was provided during MP1 was removed. Over the same time period, FADS1 activity
250 decreased. DNA damage decreased during MP1 when dietary zinc was 9.3 mg/d and 1.5 g
251 phytate/d was provided, and it remained lower throughout MP2. There was no significant
252 change in plasma glutathione concentrations throughout the study. Plasma zinc concentrations,
253 FADS2 and FADS1 activities, DNA strand breaks, and the plasma glutathione levels did not
254 differ between subjects randomized to 25 mg/d supplemental zinc versus a placebo during the
255 14-day MP3. Possibly, these biomarkers are not sensitive to short-term changes in zinc intake or
256 the method of zinc intake has a factor in these biomarkers' response (28).

257 The finding that plasma zinc concentrations remained unchanged over the course of the
258 study is consistent with the results of previous studies that have shown plasma zinc
259 concentrations respond to a moderate zinc depletion diet only if the diet is continued for several
260 months or if it is accompanied by high phytate intakes (29-31). These results are also consistent
261 with those reported by Zyba et al., who did not observe any changes in plasma zinc
262 concentrations, despite increased zinc absorption in a feeding trial with a 2-week 6 mg Zn/d
263 depletion phase followed by a 10 mg Zn/d repletion phase (12). A previous study showed that

264 plasma zinc concentrations did not change when dietary zinc moderately increased by 4 mg/d,
265 but they increased significantly after a 4-week supplementation phase while consuming an ad
266 libitum diet with 25 mg/d supplemental zinc (32). The difference in these findings may be due to
267 the longer supplementation period (4 weeks vs. 2 weeks), differences in the type of diet (ad
268 libitum vs. controlled), or in sample size.

269 FADS2 activity, estimated from the GLA:LA ratio, increased from the end of MP1 to the
270 end of MP2 when dietary zinc increased from 9.3 mg/d to 10.9 mg/d. During that period, the
271 proportion of the dietary zinc coming from the bread increased, and the additional 1.5 mg/d of
272 phytate was removed. FADS1 activity, estimated from the AA:DGLA ratio, decreased from
273 both baseline and the end of MP1 to the end of MP2. A previous low zinc study showed that
274 both enzymes' activities normalized to baseline values after an ad libitum diet with a 25 mg/d
275 zinc supplement for 4 weeks (32). Δ -6-desaturase specifically, also known as the FADS2
276 enzyme, has reduced activity during zinc deficiency, which affects the metabolism of essential
277 fatty acids (33). This is consistent with our results as we saw decreased FADS2 activity at the
278 end of MP1, when dietary zinc was lowered to 9.3 mg/d from participants' pre-study intake. It
279 then increased when dietary zinc was increased to 10.9 mg/d in MP2. We did not see any further
280 changes in FADS2 or FADS1 activities following the two-week MP3 period when half of the
281 men received a 25 mg/d zinc supplement. This may have been due to whether the zinc was
282 consumed before a meal or with a meal. Massih et al. found that consuming a 25 mg zinc
283 supplement with a meal results in higher FADS1 activity compared to when the supplement is
284 taken before the meal. However, FADS2 activity did not differ between taking the zinc
285 supplement before or with a meal (28). The lack of change during MP3 may also suggest that a

286 longer period of zinc supplementation may be required to modulate FADS1 and FADS2
287 activities.

288 DNA strand breaks was decreased at both the end of MP1 and the end of MP2 compared
289 to baseline. A decrease in DNA damage is an indicator of decreased oxidative stress, which has
290 been associated previously with zinc supplementation (16). Increasing dietary zinc by only 4
291 mg/d from 6 to 10 mg/d decreased DNA strand breaks in young men (12). In our study, the
292 increase in dietary zinc between MP1 and MP2 was only 1.6 mg/d. This increase may have been
293 insufficient to cause any changes in DNA damage. Furthermore, the moderate zinc intake of
294 10.9 mg/d in our study was lower than the reported pre-study dietary intakes of about 14.9 mg
295 Zn/d from three of the four cohorts. The result that DNA damage decreased from baseline to the
296 end of both MP1 and MP2 is the opposite of what we expect to find given the relationship
297 between zinc and DNA damage. This may have been a result of consuming a standardized diet
298 that may have been more balanced in nutrients than the participants' pre-study diets, and not due
299 to changes in dietary zinc intake specifically. In addition, we did not observe any changes to
300 DNA damage levels after the 2-week supplementation phase (MP3), which suggests that two
301 weeks is not sufficient to observe the effect of the 25 mg/d supplement on DNA damage.

302 GSH is another marker of oxidative stress, as it decreases in response to oxidative stress
303 associated with zinc deficiency (18). Interestingly, the GSH analysis showed a similar result to
304 the DNA strand breaks analysis, in that they were opposite from what was expected based on
305 reported literature. Although not statistically significant ($P=0.08$), GSH tended to be higher at
306 the end of MP1 and end of MP2 in comparison to baseline. Like the other biomarkers assessed,
307 there was no significant change in plasma glutathione levels during MP3 among the participants
308 given the 25 mg/d zinc supplement.

309 In summary, a small increase in dietary zinc of 1.6 mg/d, with approximately 58% of
310 dietary zinc being provided in the form of zinc-biofortified wheat, along with a reduction in
311 dietary phytate that caused the phytate:zinc molar ratio to change from 22.32 to 5.42
312 significantly increased FADS2 and reduced FADS1 activities in healthy men. As we observed
313 previously (12, 32), the activities of the FADS enzymes seem to be particularly sensitive to small
314 changes in dietary zinc that do not affect plasma zinc concentrations. In this study, the changes
315 in FADS2 and FADS1 activities, two measures of zinc function that are very sensitive to changes
316 in dietary zinc, from the end of MP1 to the end of MP2 showed that biofortification can be one
317 of many strategies that can improve zinc intake. While biofortification may only increase dietary
318 zinc intake by a small amount, it still contributes to improving zinc status, which is especially
319 important in the LMIC context where high phytate content of the diet inhibits zinc absorption.
320 Unfortunately, our findings are limited by sample size, the small increase and bioavailability of
321 dietary zinc between the metabolic periods, and the relatively short period of supplementation
322 during MP3. Despite these limitations, our results show that a small 1.6 mg/d increase in dietary
323 zinc intake by consuming biofortified wheat can affect the activities of FADS2 and FADS1. The
324 data suggest that FADS activity biomarkers are more sensitive to zinc intake than is plasma zinc
325 concentration. Future research is needed to determine the longer-term effects of biofortified
326 wheat consumption on additional zinc status biomarkers, i.e., measures of oxidative stress,
327 immune function, and endocrine metabolism.

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337 samples, analyzed data, and drafted the manuscript; CMM assisted with data analysis and
338 interpretation, and contributed to the writing of the manuscript; JS assisted in designing the
339 study, analyzed data, assisted with data interpretation, and reviewed the manuscript; JW
340 performed the laboratory analysis of samples, assisted with data interpretation, and reviewed the
341 manuscript; CW performed the laboratory analysis of samples, analyzed data, and reviewed the
342 manuscript; CS coordinated and implemented study procedures, and reviewed the manuscript;
343 JCK designed the study, supervised the implementation of the study, interpreted data, and
344 contributed to the writing of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Table 1. Zinc and phytate composition of the study diet during three metabolic periods

	MP1	MP2	MP3	
	All	All	Placebo (P)	Supplement (S) ¹
Dietary Zinc, mg/d	9.3	10.9	10.9	10.9
Phytate, mg/d	2096	596	596	596
Phytate:zinc molar ratio	22.32	5.42	5.42	5.42

¹During MP3, half of the participants were randomized to receive a 25 mg Zn/d supplement which was to be consumed in the morning 30 minutes before breakfast in addition to continuing with the MP2 diet. The other half continued on the MP2 diet with no supplement, and consumed a placebo pill instead.

Abbreviations: MP1—Metabolic Period 1, MP2—Metabolic Period 2, MP3—Metabolic Period

3

Table 2. Background characteristics of participants at enrollment¹

	Value
Number of men studied	36
Age, y	26±8
Ethnicity	
Asian	17 (47.2)
White	12 (33.3)
Hispanic or Latino	6 (16.7)
Black or African American	1 (2.8)
Height, m	1.75±.06
Weight, kg	74.6 ± 13.1
BMI, kg/m ²	24.4±3.6
Underweight (Below 18.5)	0 (0)
Normal (18.5-24.9)	26 (72.2)
Overweight (25-29.9)	6 (16.7)
Obese (30 and above)	4 (11.1)
Waist circumference, cm	81.9±9.1
Hemoglobin, g/dL	14.0±1.5
Blood pressure, mm Hg	
Systolic	118±10
Diastolic	76±6
Resting heart rate, bpm	70±9

¹Values are mean ± SD or *n*(%)

Table 3. Plasma zinc and GSH concentrations and GLA:LA ratio and AA:DGLA ratio in all men studied during the first two metabolic periods¹

	Baseline (n=36)	MP1 ² (n=36)	MP2 ² (n=33)	<i>P</i> ³ , MP1- Baseline	<i>P</i> ³ , MP2- Baseline	<i>P</i> ³ , MP2- MP1
Zinc, µg/dL	79.4 ± 7.2	76.0 ± 7.4	77.9 ± 0.1	0.06	0.4	0.22
GLA:LA (FADS2 activity)	0.021 ± 0.009	0.020 ± 0.007	0.025 ± 0.010	0.5	0.05	0.02
AA:DGLA (FADS1 activity)	6.38 ± 2.56	6.37 ± 2.41	5.53 ± 1.84	0.6	0.01	0.01
GSH, µM	16.4 ± 7.8	18.7 ± 8.2	18.5 ± 8.9	0.08	0.08	0.94

¹Values are estimated means ± SD from the linear mixed model.

²MP1 diet provided 9.3 mg/d of dietary zinc. MP2 diet provided 10.9 mg/d dietary zinc.

³*P* values reflect significance of effects of diet change among baseline and MPs.

Abbreviations: AA—arachidonic acid, DGLA—dihomo-gamma-linolenic acid, FADS2—fatty acid desaturase 2, FADS1—fatty acid desaturase 1, GLA—gamma-linolenic acid, GSH—glutathione, LA—linoleic acid, MP1—Metabolic Period 1, MP2—Metabolic Period 2

Table 4. Plasma zinc and GSH concentrations and GLA:LA and AA:DGLA ratios in men in the zinc supplement and placebo groups at the end of metabolic periods 2 and 3^{1,2}

	MP2P (n=17)	MP2S (n=16)	MP3P (n=16)	MP3S (n=16)	<i>P</i> ³
Zinc, µg/dL	78.0 ± 9.5	77.8 ± 9.0	75.6 ± 8.4	83.1 ± 11.4	0.16
GLA:LA (FADS2 activity)	0.023 ± 0.0092	0.027 ± 0.010	0.024 ± 0.008	0.027 ± 0.009	0.8
AA:DGLA (FADS1 activity)	5.65 ± 1.89	5.38 ± 1.83	5.65 ± 1.79	5.16 ± 1.16	0.43
GSH, µM	17.1 ± 9.4	20.0 ± 8.3	20.0 ± 9.8	17.8 ± 6.5	0.13

¹Values are estimated means ± SD from the linear mixed model. MP2 and MP3 diets provided 10.9 mg/d dietary zinc per day.

²Participants assigned to group P consumed a placebo pill in addition to the diet. Participants assigned to group S consumed a daily supplement of 25 mg zinc in addition to the diet.

³*P* values reflect significance of time * group interaction.

Abbreviations: AA—arachidonic acid, DGLA—dihomo-gamma-linolenic acid, FADS2—fatty acid desaturase 2, FADS1—fatty acid desaturase 1, GLA—gamma-linolenic acid, GSH—glutathione, LA—linoleic acid, MP2—Metabolic Period 2, MP3—Metabolic Period 3

Figure Legends

Figure 1. Omega-6 fatty acid metabolic pathway

Figure 2. Study design

Dietary zinc was controlled over the course of a zinc depletion/repletion trial. Additional zinc was provided via biofortified wheat in MP2 and a 25 mg Zn/d supplement for half of the study participants in MP3. The other study participants received a placebo pill in MP3.

Abbreviations: MP1—Metabolic Period 1, MP2—Metabolic Period 2, MP3—Metabolic Period 3, Zn—zinc

Figure 3. DNA damage among all men studied during the first two metabolic periods (A) and after assignment to the zinc supplement and placebo groups at the end of metabolic periods 2 and 3 (B)

Values are estimated means \pm SD from the linear mixed model, n=36 for baseline and MP1, n=33 for MP2, n=17 for MP2P, n=16 for MP2S, MP3P, and MP3S. *P* values reflect significance of effects of diet change from baseline to each MP.

Abbreviations: MP1—Metabolic Period 1, MP2—Metabolic Period 2, MP3—Metabolic Period 3, P—placebo, S—supplement

Zinc-Biofortified Wheat Intake and Zinc Status Biomarkers in Men: Randomized**Controlled Trial (RCT)****Erinn M. Liong****Online Supplementary Material****Supplementary Table 1. Menu items¹**

Menu Item	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4
Juice, apple	248	--	--	--
Juice, cranberry	--	245	123	245
Cereal, Kellogg's Cornflakes	42	42	42	--
Cereal, Kellogg's Rice Krispies	--	--	--	33
Milk, whole	122	61	61	61
Egg whites, cooked	134	134	134	134
Bread, whole wheat	193	193	193	193
Bread, white	--	50	--	50
Butter, salted	14	14	19	9
Margarine	14	42	42	56
Jam, regular	27	40	--	40
Tea or coffee as a beverage	490	490	490	490
Rice beverage	--	120	240	120
Apple	182	--	182	182
Watermelon	160	--	--	--
Grapes, seedless	--	98	--	98
Mango	--	160	--	--
Banana	--	--	118	--
Quinoa burger	91	--	--	--
Masala burger	--	78	--	74
Meatless breakfast patties	--	--	--	69
Carrot soup	--	--	240	--
Lettuce, mixed greens	47	47	83	55
Tomato, raw	62	62	62	62
Cucumber, raw	30	30	30	40
Celery, raw	30	--	--	--
Girard's dressing	30	30	--	--
Newman's olive oil and vinegar	--	--	27	27
Cookies, ginger	12	--	18	--
Vegetable Biryani	284	--	--	--
Punjab eggplant	--	284	--	--
Channa masala	--	--	284	--
Rice, white	71	--	--	142
Rice, brown	--	142	213	--
Fire roasted vegetables	140	--	--	--
Asian vegetables	--	--	151	--

Misto alla griglia vegetables	--	--	--	113
Tortilla, white flour	--	--	49	--
Roasted potatoes, peppers, onions	--	85	--	--
Chutney	--	34	--	--
Yogurt, blueberries or vanilla	--	113	--	113
Popsicle, mango & cream	40	--	--	80

¹Values are portion sizes (g). Participants were on the study diet seven days a week. The menu was a four-day cycling menu, with days 1-3 repeating each week.

Supplementary Table 2. Fatty acid plasma concentrations in all men studied during the first two metabolic periods¹

	Baseline (n=36)	MP1² (n=36)	MP2² (n=33)	P³, MP1- Baseline	P³, MP2- Baseline	P³, MP2- MP1
LA, mM	1.270±0.230	1.370±0.160	1.440±0.340	0.07	0.002	0.36
GLA, mM	0.027±0.012	0.027±0.009	0.034±0.012	0.98	0.003	0.05
DGLA, mM	0.131±0.044	0.118±0.032	0.130±0.032	0.08	0.92	0.05
AA, mM	0.753±0.159	0.695±0.148	0.686±0.181	0.0003	0.00008	0.35

¹Values are estimated means ± SD from the linear mixed model.

²MP1 diet provided 9.3 mg/d of dietary zinc. MP2 diet provided 10.9 mg/d of dietary zinc.

³P values reflect significance of effects of diet change among baseline and MPs.

Abbreviations: AA—arachidonic acid, DGLA—dihomo-gamma-linolenic acid, GLA—gamma-linolenic acid, LA—linoleic acid, MP1—Metabolic Period 1, MP2—Metabolic Period 2

Supplementary Table 3. Fatty acid plasma concentrations in men in the zinc supplement and placebo groups at the end of metabolic periods 2 and 3^{1,2}

	MP2P (n=17)	MP2S (n=16)	MP3P (n=16)	MP3S (n=16)	P³
LA, mM	1.463±0.287	1.416±0.395	1.415±0.286	1.328±0.208	0.78
GLA, mM	0.032±0.012	0.036±0.014	0.034±0.014	0.035±0.013	0.54
DGLA, mM	0.122±0.030	0.140±0.032	0.132±0.034	0.140±0.024	0.64
AA, mM	0.654±0.159	0.722±0.203	0.706±0.153	0.716±0.160	0.43

¹Values are estimated means ± SD from the linear mixed model. MP2 and MP3 diets provided 10.9 mg/d of dietary zinc.

²Participants assigned to group P consumed a placebo pill in addition to the diet. Participants assigned to group S consumed a daily supplement of 25 mg zinc in addition to the diet.

³P values reflect significance of group * time interaction.

Abbreviations: AA—arachidonic acid, DGLA—dihomo-gamma-linolenic acid, GLA—gamma-linolenic acid, LA—linoleic acid, MP2—Metabolic Period 2, MP3—Metabolic Period 3